

Quantum Two-Slit Interference Applied to a Coin Part 2

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In Part 1, we tried to create a toy model involving a rotating-translating coin. We examined what kind of interaction is needed to create a typical 2-slit interference pattern. Here we examine a physical object, namely a photon, which has a built-in periodic cycle for its electric and magnetic fields. These are perpendicular and in plane perpendicular to motion and both change as $\cos(-Et/\hbar + px/\hbar)$. We point out that the electric and magnetic fields are both real, they are not described by $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ and furthermore, they are deterministic, not probabilistic. We try to see how such a picture can lead to quantum two slit interference.

Basically, we argue that if one only considers the electric field, long range interactions from atoms around both slits interact with a photon heading towards the center between the slits. As a result, the physical interaction must involve both slits, but one has no idea through which slit the photon passes. There is probability in the problem, but at the same time interactions with both slits before the photon passes through and also after. One needs a model which captures both the notion of probability and interaction with both slits. For probability this should be an OR situation (one slit or the other), but it cannot be the usual classical probability scheme which implies that moving through one slit only involves interaction with that slit. Interactions with both slits occur. This seems like a contradiction because one applies OR probability to one slit or another. Given that the interaction with the electric field occurs in a periodic manner $\cos(-Et+px)/\hbar=1$, we suggest that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ with its modulus of 1 captures the idea that any electric field position as the same probability, but that there is periodic motion linked with interaction in space.

. As a result, one may keep the mathematical notion of an OR probability scheme by introducing an interacting probability $\exp(ipx)$. This means that the probabilities from each slit in the OR (add) scheme interfere or interact which is what is required because an interaction with both slits occurs. $\exp(ipx)$ captures the periodicity and also enforces conservation of momentum ($\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp((p_1+p_2)x)$) and it seems that this is the only information needed.

Photon Properties

The notion of a photon was developed by Maxwell from his electromagnetic equations long before quantum mechanics was developed. He found that if a photon moves in a particular direction, then there are perpendicular electric and magnetic fields in a plane perpendicular to this motion. Both the electric and magnetic fields change as:

$$\cos(-E/\hbar t + p/\hbar x) \text{ where } x \text{ is the direction of motion } ((1))$$

There is no complex $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ from quantum mechanics in ((1)), nor is there any notion of probability. It was known before Maxwell that photons interfere when passing through two slits, but this was ascribed to wave interference (like water wave interference). It seems that it was Einstein in 1905 (with the photoelectric effect) who argued that photon energy is not distributed in space in a wavelike manner. This then begs the question: How does one describe photon

2-slit interference? In Part I, we introduced a toy model involving a spinning coin which also translates. Here we suggest that a photon already has a natural periodic motion and the toy model of Part 1 may apply.

A Photon and 2-Slits from the Point of View of the Electric Field

To simplify matters, we consider only interactions involving the photon electric field. If this is a true electric field it should interact with the electric fields of charged electrons in the atoms in the 2-slit apparatus. It is also known that if there were no slits, the photon could not pass through the metal of the apparatus. Assuming the photon remains as one object, it must pass through one slit or the other. This is, however, a probabilistic problem because if one sends the photon in towards the center (between the slits), there is no way of knowing through which slit it will pass. Furthermore, the photon must interact with electric fields from both slits.

This makes matters complicated because in the usual OR case of classical probability, one slit or the other implies:

Interaction with one slit or the other, but not with both ((2))

We suggest that physically the photon must interact with electric fields from both slits while entering and leaving the apparatus. The usual classical OR approach must be modified. Given that one must use probabilities and that these pertain to one slit OR the other, one should have a probability for each, but this scheme must include interaction with both slits. We suggest that this can happen if the probabilities themselves interact (or interference) in a manner which is consistent with the physics of the system, i.e the periodicity of the electric field and conservation of momentum.

Given that the electric and magnetic fields changes as $\cos(-Et+px)$ ($\hbar=1$), one may use a probability:

$$\exp(-iEt+ipx) \quad ((3))$$

In this case, interaction is only in space, so we only utilise $\exp(ipx)$ from ((3))

$\exp(ipx)$ is a probability (not an electric field). Its unit modulus squared means that any position of the electric field has the same probability (or any x position has the same probability), but it contains the spatial periodicity of the electric field and ensures conservation of momentum:

$$\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x) \quad ((4))$$

We suggest that this is the only physical information one needs to retain and with $\exp(ipx)$, it is encapsulated into the probability. One may then write:

$$\exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_1) + \exp(i \mathbf{p} \cdot \mathbf{r}_2) \quad ((5))$$

Here r_1 is a vector from slit 1 to a point x on a screen far away, while r_2 is a vector from the center of the second slit to the same x point. These two rays are approximately parallel and are associated with a single angle θ_2 (mentioned in Part 1) which the rays make with a y -axis (i.e. an axis perpendicular to the 2-slit apparatus).

The interference of the probability (which is a math procedure) allows one to retain the probabilistic notion of an OR situation adding, while at the same showing that interactions with both slits, and not one occur. The results of the interaction are expressed in terms of a probability distribution, but one must take the modulus squared of ((5)) to obtain this positive valued function.

As a result, $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ for a photon is a mathematical manner of introducing a probability which may be used in AND (multiply) and OR (add) scenarios while at the same time allowing for non-point interactions, i.e. interactions spread out in space.

In our description above we did not mention the spatial separation of the slits. The electric field undergoes periodic motion while traveling a distance of:

$$\text{Wavelength} = \hbar/p \quad ((6))$$

If one considers that changing electric field values in this wavelength range to be of key physical importance (because afterwards they just repeat themselves), then one might expect that the slits should be about a wavelength apart as well. In other words, it seems that one does not just have an OR situation, but one in which interactions occur within \hbar/p in space instead of at a point. If this is the case, then the ideas applied above to the photon might equally well apply to a particle with mass.

Particle With Mass

In the above description, we relied heavily on the periodic motion of the electric field. The final result, however, was that one has an interaction range of

$$\hbar/p \quad ((7))$$

and periodic interacting probability of $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

There is no reason that one cannot try to apply these notions to a particle with mass to see if it too can create two-slit interference. In fact, experiments show that it does. This seems to suggest that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ (with $-Et+px$ being a Lorentz invariant) has a deeper root than simply the changing photon electric field. We have suggested in previous notes that this root lies in the Lorentz invariant $-E\Delta t + p\Delta x = 0$ with

$$\Delta t = \hbar/E \text{ and } \Delta x = \hbar/p \quad ((8))$$

We, however, consider the photon because it has physical periodicity and we suggest that the toy model developed in Part 1 should apply to it.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we developed a toy model in Part 1 based on a spinning and translating coin and tried to describe an interaction which would produce the results of two slit interference. Here we consider Maxwell's photon with its changing electric and magnetic fields following $\cos(-Et+px)$, ($\hbar=1$). Instead of using the notion of physical waves to account for two slit interference, we suggest that one must use the idea of probability. A photon cannot pass through a solid piece of metal and if it is sent towards the center between two slits, it must pass through one or the other (if it remains as one object). This involves the idea of probability, in fact an OR situation (slit 1 or 2).

The problem is that the photon's electric field interacts with charges near both slits and so this is not a slit 1 only or slit 2 only (mutually exclusive) case. If one wishes to use formal OR probability math (add), then one must include the fact that interactions with both slits occur both before and after the photon passes through the apparatus. We suggest that one can describe probability and interaction by creating an interacting probability (i.e. an interfering probability in space). Such a probability must capture the key physical information required, namely the periodicity $-Et+px$, the notion that a single photon has equal probability to be at any x , i.e. have the electric field at any value and that momentum should be conserved (and energy too). This leads to $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$. For a 2-slit problem, there is only interaction in space and so only $\exp(ipx)$ is used. This leads to: $\exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2)$. Taking the modulus squared leads to a real value distribution. The point is that $\exp(ipx)$ allows one to take a physical situation in which there is interaction with two slits and break it into a probabilistic OR which looks classical (using a plus sign), but an interacting probability (interference) shows that one does not have mutually exclusive events at the interaction level. Whether the photon goes through one slit or the other, it interacts with both, we argue.